

HUMAN RESOURCES PLANNING MANAGEMENT ON CONSTRUCTION SITES

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Abstract

Purpose – One of the main objectives of a manager must be to study the ways of applying different technologies, so that by applying them the company is successful. When the objectives are met and the company is successful, it can expand both its production and the market for its products.

Methodology/approach – The rapid access to the results of various researches and their implementation in a large number of countries is the result of the phenomenon of globalization. Increasing productivity, modernizing technological flows, reducing the execution time in making a product while improving its quality, are basic priorities of any manager.

Findings – Achieving the goals of the organization and increasing performance within the company can be achieved by applying efficient management. If the manager has access to information, both in the country and abroad, the success of the company is possible. The theories studied must be able to be put into practice and be appropriate to the specifics of the field in which they are applied.

Research limitations/implications – The paper presents the results of the research, which aims to study the work teams in a process in the field of construction. This study was carried out in order to be able to effectively form work formations in the case of construction works. Different working conditions and the composition of the work formations are taken into account.

Practical implications – Managers must decide within the company to apply those procedures that lead to its success. After establishing the objectives and the methods by which they can be achieved, the managers must find ways in which the techniques can be successfully applied within the company and then the globalization of these solutions at the widest possible level.

Originality/value – The study analyzed different factors that can influence the composition of a work formation, within a construction process. The study is based on the use of the multi-criteria method. This study aims at compiling an optimal work team and formulating conclusions regarding the most rational and efficient use of work teams in the construction activity.

Key words: Management, globalization, constructions,

Introduction

The creation of new products, the implementation of an improved technology, the application of efficient organizational procedures, the use of operational management methods, etc., are just some of the results of human activity and which are entirely attributed to him. In the activity of creating products and services, highlighting the importance of human, it should not be seen as an under estimation of other resources such as material, financial or information. Achieving the objectives in a productive activity can be achieved only when the human factor is considered in close connection with all other resources. Carrying out the activity under normal conditions, developing the production, increasing the market of products, globalizing the production, respectively making a profit, are just some of the main objectives of a company, which can be achieved only when, among all the resources involved in productive activity, a dynamic balance can be achieved.

Initial data

Studies show that multicriteria analysis can be used successfully in various fields of activity. Since 1960, this method has been applied as a way of making a decision. Today, it is frequently used in project management. [Beria et al., 2011]

The purpose of the method is to determine an order of results, by comparative estimates, applied to different possible alternatives. It is used when the people involved in making a decision face a certain problem. The analysis is useful in situations where, in order to make a decision, in solving a problem, a single criterion cannot lead to the determination of a satisfactory result. The role of the method is to systematize and combine several analyzed variants, which are necessary and useful in order to make a decision. The decision will be influenced by how these variants each contribute to the final result. The multicriteria analysis highlights the arguments and subjective opinions of the participants regarding all the analyzed situations; summarizes the opinions presented in order to obtain a succession according to the importance of the analyzed elements; identifies possible contradictory states; makes recommendations and proposes operational advice. [Roman, M., 2012]

Case Study

Establishing the decision-making context

We will take for analysis, several variants of composing a team of workers, in the field of construction. The composition of the team will be made according to certain characteristics (age, qualification, seniority, etc.). We will analyze the composition of the teams, and the most favorable combination will be determined, which will be as close as possible to the current requirements and needs of a company.

Criteria and value range

- *Age of employees.* This characteristic can underline the appearance of the aging process and the need to hire young staff within the company;
- *Performance - seniority in work.* The young staff will have more work power and, implicitly, they will be eager to perform. More experienced workers can perform better jobs, from a qualitative point of view, but they can also have certain salary or social advantages that the company must take into account;
- *Based on this analysis,* it will be possible to highlight the existence of a plus or minus of workers of a certain specialization in the company, which will obviously be transferred or requalified, possibly hiring where appropriate. [Hossu et.al., 2001].

Table no. 1. Criteria and value ranges

Criteria	Indicators	Value ranges	
C ₁	Performance	Seniority in work - experience gained at work	1- 5
C ₂	Age	Average age of the team	25 - 50 years
C ₃	Specialization	One or more specializations within the team	1- 5
C ₄	Cooperation within the team	Balance between team members	1- 5
C ₅	Composition of work formations	Depending on the number of workers who can perform an activity	1- 5

- The composition of the work formations will be done so that the respective team can carry out a productive activity. Too many workers in the team means waste, too few workers will lead to the impossibility of carrying out that activity safely. Manufacturing companies make up their work teams so that they are able to perform certain well-established tasks.

- Cooperation. In order for team members to be able to carry out their duties in optimal working conditions, they must be productive and perform well. Team members must work together with the main goal of achieving the set objectives.

Performance matrix

On the lines of the matrix there are represented the options taken into account in the analysis and on the columns the performances of the options related to the chosen criteria are represented. The value assessment of the performance of each option can be done numerically, or using any other form of evaluation that allows clear highlighting of results.

Table no. 2. Performance matrix

Criteria \ Alternatives	C ₁	C ₂	...C _j	C _n
A ₁	a ₁₁	a ₁₂	a ₁₃	a _{1n}
A ₂	a ₂₁	a ₂₂	a ₂₃	a _{2n}
...A _i	a _{ij}	...
A _n	a _{m1}	a _{m2}	a _{m3}	a _{mn}

General representation of the performance matrix, with m rows and n columns [Roman, M., 2012]

In the process of creating products, especially in the field of construction, the organization of production and work has an essential role, as they study a series of technical, organizational and economic regulations that make the workforce and technological processes to be used as appropriate and efficient as possible. Thus, through the process of globalization of productive activities, positive results can be obtained in many fields of activity, by extending processes or products from the company level, to the level of a country and then worldwide.

Human is considered by specialists as the only component within a company, who can create value for use. [Nicolescu, O., 1997]

Estimated values of the alternatives for criteria

The options express the way in which the variants of proposals meet the proposed objectives. The most favorable option will be chosen from those options that will be considered the closest to the proposed objectives. [Mircea, A.T., 2016] The criterion expresses the value according to which the evaluations are made and the options are compared, in order to determine to what extent the options lead to the achievement of the established objectives. [Dobre et al, 2000]

Taking into account some basic criteria, we can analyze the organization of work and teams, within the productive activities specific to the construction field. We can mention the following criteria:

- specialization of workers in work teams;
- collaboration between team members;
- ensuring the necessary climate for collaboration between teams;
- ensuring a work front for each team, as well as the organization corresponding to the activity carried out (appropriate work space, material storage, circulation, etc.);
- creating the necessary conditions (development) for the execution of the technological process;
- ensuring the continuity of the workforce force activity, during the production process; [Popa, A., 2006]
- the use of work norms, for as many of the activities carried out on the site as possible;
- stimulation and motivation of the work submitted by employees (awards, bonuses, individual or group incentives, facilities, social protection programs, etc.);

- ensuring the necessary support for the continuous improvement of the staff, corresponding to the qualification and the activity carried out;
- the composition of the teams of workers to be realized according to the current requirements of the market;
- continuous training and improvement of the workforce in the field where it operates.

The study analyzes four teams of workers, taking into account different criteria's that we considered relevant. Four of these criteria are evaluated qualitatively, one of the criteria is numerical.

Table no. 3. Estimated values of the alternatives for criteria

Alternatives	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅
Team A ₁	5	20	5	4	4
Team A ₂	3	30	4	5	5
Team A ₃	3	40	3	2	3
Team A ₄	4	50	2	3	2

Criteria considered in the analysis:

1 - unimportant; 2 – less unimportant; 3 – a bit important; 4 - important; 5 - very important

Scores and weights

The data in the basic matrix are, in most cases, transformed into numerical values. This is done in two phases.

- Scores: for all the variants considered in the analysis, a score is established, depending on the importance and which is applied to each criterion.
- Weights: determines, for all criteria, the relative evaluation between the highest and lowest value of the size chosen for comparisons. [AMC, manual, 2009]

Weights estimated directly

In the example, we will use direct estimation to determine the relative importance of the weights for each analyzed criterion. A criterion with a higher weight is more important. The determination of direct estimation is generally done by qualified persons, who take into account the wishes of the companies regarding the elements according to which the decisions are made, but they must be prepared to translate these wishes into relative weights. [Roman, M., 2012]

In this case, we considered: for criterion C₁ - performance and C₃ - specialization, which are the most important elements, we allocated a weight of 30%, the other criteria have a lower importance, with a weight of 20% for criterion C₂ - age, respectively 10% being allocated to criterion C₄ - cooperation within the team and C₅ - composition of work teams.

Table no. 4. Weights estimated directly

Criteria	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅
Weight	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.10	0.10

Normalized performance matrix

In order to be able to compare the results of the analyzed elements, the scores of the criteria must be transformed so that they are represented by the same units of measurement. This is done by normalization. Through this activity we aim to obtain, for the determined values of the criteria, a common unit of measurement so that we can compare the obtained results.

Normalization will be achieved by the method of linear transformation:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{a_j^{max}} \quad a_j^{max} = \max_i \{a_{ij}\} \text{ for maximum effect}$$

$$r_{ij} = 1 - \frac{a_{ij}}{a_j^{max}} = \frac{a_j^{max} - a_{ij}}{a_j^{max}} \text{ - for minimum effect [Dobre et al, 2007]}$$

The nominal values will result from applying the linear transformation method. We will calculate the standardized value for each alternative and for each criterion.

Table no. 5. Normalized performance matrix

Alternatives	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅
Team A ₁	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.20	0.20
Team A ₂	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.00	0.00
Team A ₃	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.40
Team A ₄	0.20	0.00	0.60	0.40	0.60

Multicriteria evaluation – results by summing the weights

$$A_{Si} = \sum_{j=1}^n W_j r_{ij} \quad [\text{Dobre et al, 2007}]$$

r_{ij} – standardized scores, related to the criteria;

W_j – the weight of each criterion;

A_{Si} – total score for each alternative.

Table no. 6. Results by summing the weights

Alternatives	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	A _{Si}
Team A ₁	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.20	0.20	0.16
Team A ₂	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.00	0.30
Team A ₃	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.40	0.60	0.38
Team A ₄	0.20	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.40	0.28
Weight	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.10	0.10	

Fig. no. 1. The total score of the teams

Hierarchy of weights

Using this method in decision making can provide important data and the results obtained can be a real help in making a decision related to a certain issue.

Discussion and conclusions

The following conclusions were based on the study:

- the best alternative was for Team A3, where a score of 0.38 was achieved, for the criteria of the greatest importance: the performance and specialization of the team;
- for Team A2 a score of 0.30 resulted;
- for the A4 team a score of 0.28 resulted;
- respectively for Team A1 a score of 0.16.

It can be seen that the maximum efficiency is achieved by the A3 team made up of experienced workers, whose goal is to achieve the work tasks, have work power, the average age being 40 years. For inexperienced young teams it is more difficult to mobilize to work together and be productive. There is also the possibility that some tasks may not be performed without sufficient knowledge. At an older age, there may be problems with salary increases, various salary or social benefits. It also highlights the phenomenon of aging and the need to hire young staff.

Teams fail to perform their work tasks when one or more of the following causes occurs:

- they are assigned activities for which they do not have the necessary qualification;
- the teams are not made up so that they can perform a certain activity;
- they are not provided with the necessary conditions to perform the tasks;
- there is no good collaboration between the members, within the team;
- conflicts occur within the team;
- workers do not have the same interests or common concerns;
- communication between team members in performing tasks is not very well done;
- the transmission of information between the team and the higher levels is interrupted.

Each worker must have a well-established role in the team, and the distribution of tasks must be done according to their qualification. The composition of the teams should be done as rationally as possible with a clear specification of the level of responsibility for each member of the team and the members with decision-making rights. Responsibilities and decisions must be in accordance with the knowledge and training of each worker. On-the-job training, qualification and continuous improvement, according to the requirements of the workplace, are important for improving the employee's performance.

When the composition of the work formations is done in accordance with the activity carried out, then a larger amount of work will be performed per unit of time. In the construction activity, there are many activities for the realization of which, workers with a different degree of qualification are needed. Some operations are performed by unskilled workers, other operations require higher qualification. The number of workers in the teams depends on the type of process performed. When an adequate team is determined to carry out a construction process, with increased productivity in carrying out tasks, it can be used through the process of globalization, both at the level of several companies within the country and at a more extensive level.

On construction sites, there are still many activities that are performed manually or semi-mechanized. In this sense, the study of the efficient organization of the productive activity is considered important. The rational use of workforce, equipment and materials and other resources, in order to determine the shortest possible time for a construction, is an important goal for companies. Increasing workforce productivity, the quality of products made, while reducing the total cost are also permanent concerns for running a company.

For this purpose, the following is continuously pursued: the rational use of the workforce force, the diminution of the manually performed activities, the mechanization, the automation, as well as the use of an execution technology adequate to the work processes.

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